

General procedure: Lead(IV) acetate (11.3 mmol) was added in portions in the presence of catalyst amount of iodine (1 g) to the steroidal diol (1.78 mmol) dissolved in dry benzene (90 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 10 h and the progress of reaction was monitored by tlc. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the residue was taken in ether. The ethereal solution was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Evaporation of the solvent gave a solid which was recrystallised from methanol to yield the products (Table 1).

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Synthesis and Biological Evaluation of some Novel *N*-[2-(Phenoxy/bromo/nitro/substituted-phenoxy)acetyl/propionyl]carbazole

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PHENOXYACETIC acid, phenoxypropionic acid, and carbazole and its various derivatives possess a wide spectrum of biological activities¹. These results prompted us to undertake the synthesis of some new *N*-[2-phenoxy/bromo/nitro/substituted-phenoxy)acetyl/propionyl]carbazole (1) and to screen their anti-inflammatory and anticonvulsant properties.

The carbazole derivatives of the compounds have been synthesised by reacting substituted

phenoxy derivatives with sodium salt of chloroacetic/propionic acids in good yields. The structures of all the compounds have been established on the basis of spectral data and elemental analysis (Table 1)

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Experimental

Melting points were determined on a Toshniwal apparatus and are uncorrected. Purity of the compounds were checked by tlc. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 157 spectrophotometer. Various phenoxy acetic acid, propionic acid their bromo, nitro substituted derivatives were synthesised by condensing the sodium salt of the appropriate phenol with $\text{ClCH}_2\text{COONa}$ and $\text{ClCH}(\text{CH}_3)\text{COONa}$. To a solution of aryloxy acid (0.04 mol in 50 ml of $\text{C}_6\text{H}_6/\text{EtOAc}$) was added thionyl chloride (0.05 mol) and the mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 8 h. The acid chloride was added dropwise to an ice-cold solution of carbazole (0.036 mol in 25 ml EtOAc) and 2*N* NaOH solution (5 ml) with constant stirring. The separated amide was filtered, washed and purified over a column of silica gel. Ir spectra displayed principal absorptions at 2900–2930 (CH_3), 1600–1330 (aromatic NO_2), 1228–1240 ($\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{N}$), 1110–1250 ($\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C}$) and 690–720 cm^{-1} (aromatic substitution pattern).

Biological evaluation: Anti-inflammatory activity of the compounds (1a–l) were tested in albino rats weighing 100–120 g (fated overnight) by the reported method². The percentage inhibition of inflammation after 3 h was calculated³. The results suggested that compounds 1b, c, j, k, l displayed promising activity which is nearly equal to that of the standard drug ibuprofen.

The anticonvulsant activity of all the compounds was recorded following the reported method⁴. The results suggested that the compounds 1b, c, j, k, l exhibited greater anticonvulsant activity using pentylenetetrazole.

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TABLE I - PHYSICAL DATA OF THE CARBAZOLES (1)*

Compd. no.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	R	Mol. formula	Yield %	M.p.** °C
1a	H	H	H	H	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₂ N	69	238-40 ^a
1b	Br	H	Br	Br	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₃ O ₂ NBr ₃	62	206-08 ^a
1c	NO ₂	H	NO ₂	NO ₂	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₄	58	234-36 ^b
1d	NO ₂	H	H	H	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂	66	230-32 ^a
1e	H	NO ₂	H	H	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂	63	238-40 ^b
1f	H	H	NO ₂	H	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂	65	238-40 ^a
1g	CH ₃	H	H	H	H	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₂ N	67	238-40 ^a
1h	H	CH ₃	H	H	H	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₂ N	64	98-100 ^a
1i	H	H	CH ₃	H	H	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₂ N	69	238-40 ^a
1j	Br	H	Br	Br	CH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ O ₂ NBr	73	228-30 ^b
1k	NO ₂	H	NO ₂	NO ₂	CH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₄	61	228-30 ^a
1l	H	H	H	H	CH ₃	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₂ N	68	220-22 ^b

*All compounds showed satisfactory analytical results for C, H and N.
 **Solvents for crystallisation: ^aMeOH, ^bMe₂CO, ^cC₆H₆.

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Scheme 1

Thiocarbazine acids. Part-III. Synthesis of 1,2,4-Triazole Derivatives

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IN continuation of our studies on the chemistry of carbon oxysulphide¹, we now report the reaction of benzyl-β-phenyl thiocarbazine (1)² with alkyl/aryl isothiocyanates and isocyanates.

Compound 1 on treatment with alkyl/aryl isothiocyanates (Scheme 1), afforded the corresponding 1-phenyl-4-alkyl/aryl-5-thio-1,2,4-triazolidin-3-ones (2; Table I). One of the compounds, viz. 1,4-diphenyl-5-thio-1,2,4-triazolidin-3-one (2a; R=Ph) showed ir band (nujol) at 1730 cm⁻¹ (C=O). Its pmr spectrum (DMSO-d₆) showed signals at δ 5.8 (1H, s, NH) and 7.3-8.0 (10H, m, ArH).

TABLE I - PHYSICAL AND IR SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2-4

Compd. no.	R	Mol. formula	Yield %	M p, °C	ν _{C=O} , cm ⁻¹
2a	Phenyl	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₃ SO	65	217	1730
2b	p-Tolyl	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₃ SO	63	231	1725
2c	p-Chlorophenyl	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₃ SOCl	67	251	1735
2d	p-Anisyl	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₃ SO ₂	68	220	1715
2e	Methyl	C ₉ H ₉ N ₃ SO	62	235	1705
3a	Phenyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂ S	91	147	-
3b	p-Chlorophenyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂ SCl	92	168	-
3c	1-Naphthyl	C ₂₅ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₂ S	91	175	-
3d	Cyclohexyl	C ₂₁ H ₂₉ N ₃ O ₂ S	91	165	-
4a	Phenyl	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂	81	166	1780 1710 1782
4b	p-Chlorophenyl	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₃ O ₂ Cl	84	206	1720 1785
4c	1-Naphthyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂	79	225	1710 1790
4d	Cyclohexyl	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂	76	215	1715